

An analysis of the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) market in Colombia from the perspective of organizational cybernetics and complexity sciences.

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Abstract

This article examines the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) market in Colombia from the perspective of organizational cybernetics and complexity studies, suggesting that it should be understood as a multifaceted adaptive system with feedback, emergence, self-organization, and nonlinear interactions. The main theoretical currents underpinning this analysis are investigated through a bibliometric analysis based on the Dialnet, ScienceDirect, and Scopus databases. This study finds connections between system dynamics, general systems theory, the viable systems model, and collective intelligence.

It suggests that, rather than functioning as a linear system, the LPG industry has a socio-technical structure that requires self-regulation and continuous adaptation strategies in the face of economic, regulatory, and technological differences. Finally, the theoretical and practical ramifications for the competitiveness of the Colombian industry and sustainable energy planning are discussed.

Keywords: energy, complexity, LPG, organizational cybernetics, complex systems, viable systems, and collective intelligence

Introduction

One of the most important energy sources in Colombia's energy matrix is liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), which is a fundamental part of the so-called liquid fuel basket.

Although LPG is widely used in the commercial, industrial, and residential sectors, research on the subject has been scarce and has focused on technical infrastructure, economic analysis, or regulation, without taking into account the complexity of its dynamics and structure.

In this sense, the behavior of LPG as a complex adaptive system can be approached from a new perspective thanks to complexity sciences. According to this perspective, interactions between government, businesses, users, and the environment produce behaviors that cannot be explained by conventional linear models. According to Mitchell (2009) and Ladyman (2013), complex systems have features in common with contemporary energy systems, such as self-organizing qualities, sensitivity to initial conditions, and unexpected dynamics.

The Colombian LPG sector is also socio-technical, as it encompasses social dynamics, market processes, legal frameworks, and physical infrastructure. Each of these components interacts with the others to create a complex network of relationships in which small disturbances (such as regulatory changes or fluctuations in the global price of crude oil) can have a significant impact on the entered supply chain.

According to Stafford Beer's organizational cybernetics (1991), the LPG industry can be considered a viable system that needs to find a balance between control, autonomy, and adaptation in order to remain sustainable in the long term.

Thus, examining its self-regulation and control systems becomes essential to understanding how the industry manages disturbances and preserves its sustainability.

Furthermore, to characterize energy processes as networks of continuous interaction, complementary techniques such as collective intelligence, Bertalanffy's general systems theory (201i), and Aaron's system dynamics (2016) must be included. These methods help to understand the structure of the system, as well as its adaptive behavior in the face of contemporary issues such as environmental sustainability, energy transition, and the digital transformation of the Colombian energy industry.

The article is divided into sections. First, the theoretical framework is presented, outlining the conceptual foundations of viable systems, organizational cybernetics, and complex systems. Next, the methodology is explained, with an emphasis on systemic modeling and

bibliometric analysis. The following sections examine the results and address the ramifications of the intricate strategy for LPG management. Finally, conclusions and suggestions on energy policy and industry competitiveness are presented.

1. Conceptual structure

The theoretical approach of this study applies various strands of systems thinking and complexity science to the analysis of the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) market in Colombia.

Complexity theory, organizational cybernetics, collective intelligence, the viable systems model (VSM), general systems theory (GST), and functionalism are the six main approaches that highlight techniques based on system dynamics.

1.1 Complexity as a method of analyzing the LPG system

Understanding systems composed of several interdependent components that interact in a nonlinear way to produce emergent behaviors that cannot be predicted from the separate components is the goal of the study of complexity Mitchell (2009); Ladyman (2013).

These interactions in the context of the Colombian LPG business involve production, transportation, storage, distribution, and consumption flows, all of which are influenced by external variables (such as global crude oil prices, exchange rates, and regulations) and internal factors (demand variability, storage capacity, and logistical efficiency).

The LPG system functions similarly to an open network, where market interactions, regulation, and operation produce continuous feedback. The stability and adaptability of the system are determined by this feedback.

The following characteristics define the behavior of LPG as a complex system (Goldenfeld, 1999):

- a) Nonlinearity: small adjustments in a single variable can have disproportionate results.
- b) Emergence: the system exhibits collective characteristics that are not present in its constituent elements.
- c) Self-organization: actors and companies modify their actions independently of a centralized authority.
- d) Sensitivity to initial conditions: changes in the financial or regulatory environment produce different trajectories.
- e) Adaptability: when the environment changes, the system adjusts its structure.

1.2 Systemic control and organizational cybernetics

Stafford Beer created organizational cybernetics in 1972, which provides a framework for understanding how complex organizations can continue to function in changing environments. Harmony between autonomy, control, and communication is its main focus.

When applied to LPG, this theory allows us to identify the ways in which the Colombian energy system preserves its operational balance despite regulatory fluctuations and the volatility of the global oil market.

Espinosa (2011) asserts that applying cybernetics to energy systems allows for the creation of intelligent organizations that can react to disturbances through decentralized control, adaptive learning, and efficient feedback.

1.3 Knowledge networks and collective intelligence

The ability of a community or network to combine the information, experiences, and choices of its members to produce better results than any individual could produce alone is known as collective intelligence (Lévy, 2012).

Producers, distributors, regulators, customers, and government organizations make up the continuous learning network in the LPG business. This network can increase the resilience of the system if it is articulated through efficient information flows.

1.4 System dynamics and general systems theory (GST)

According to Bertalanffy's general systems theory (2011), each system must be examined as a cohesive whole. In this way, the LPG sector can be considered an open system that interacts with its environment to share resources, energy, and information.

Social systems, such as the energy sector, are self-referential and autopoietic, meaning that they replicate themselves through their own communications, according to Luhmann (2015). Consequently, Colombian LPG continues to function thanks to the continuous communication between institutional actors, technological procedures, and regulations.

From a methodological point of view, this strategy is reinforced by Forrester's (1993) system dynamics, which models the feedback loops found in LPG using causal loops.

Figure 4: Simplified causal diagram of the Colombian LPG system

Source: the author 2023.

Colombian LPG has both positive and negative feedback, as illustrated in this graph.

Prices rise in response to increased demand, and the government intervenes by controlling tariffs or subsidies, which alters supply and demand and causes systemic volatility.

These cyclical processes are typical of complex adaptive systems, in which opposing forces interact to provide stability Holland (1996).

2. Approach

This study uses a hybrid methodology that incorporates systematic modeling of the Colombian liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) market with bibliometric analysis. We can understand the functional dynamics of the national energy system, as well as the conceptual framework of current knowledge, using both approaches.

2.1 General strategy

The analytical approach is based on the idea that the LPG sector should be examined as a complex adaptive system, in which economic, physical, social, and regulatory elements converge. Therefore, a methodological triangulation approach combining document review, systemic simulation, and knowledge network analysis is preferred (Creswell, 2017).

2.2 Bibliometric analysis

The bibliometric study, conducted using VOSviewer 1.6.19 soQware, drew on the Scopus, ScienceDirect, and Dialnet databases. Topics included energy systems, organizational cybernetics, complex systems, viable system models, and the LPG sector.

With an emphasis on the fields of engineering, energy, environmental sciences, and social sciences, nearly 35,000 relevant records were found. Complexity, systemic approach, feedback, self-organization, energy transition, and Colombia were the terms that appeared most frequently in co-occurrences.

Figure 1 shows a bibliometric concept map of simulated thematic co-occurrences.

Source: VosViewer simulation, own elaboration (2025).

2.3 Systemic modeling of LPG in Colombia

A conceptual model was developed that describes the causal links between the main variables in the LPG industry—production, imports, demand, prices, regulation, and subsidies—based on system dynamics and bibliometric results.

Forrester's (1993) ideas on feedback loops served as the basis for the development of the model. Two main categories of loops were distinguished:

- Self-reinforcing positive loop: price increase → imports → temporary expansion of supply → excess capacity → price decrease.
- Price increase → decrease in demand → governmentation → price stabilization is a negative (stabilizing) loop.

2.4 Cybernetic interpretation

The main objective of the cybernetic study was to identify the self-regulating and self-organizing processes of the LPG system. Beer (1991) states that a system's ability to adapt to disturbances without losing its functional character is what determines its survivability.

This viability in the LPG sector is demonstrated by the cooperation of organizations such as the Mining and Energy Planning Unit (UPME), the Ministry of Mines and Energy (MinMinas), the Energy and Gas Regulatory Commission (CREG), and distribution companies. These organizations work together to create a multilevel system that maintains operational balance through information flows and control.

3. Results and evaluation

The systemic analysis revealed three significant new dynamics in the behavior of the Colombian LPG industry: adaptive feedback, coevolution, and self-organization.

3.1 Self-organization

The way in which LPG distribution and transportation companies modify their operations in response to governmental or financial changes is an example of self-organization.

For example, companies adjust their distribution, storage, and transportation plans when the CREG modifies price limits or marketing margins.

Without the need for centralized management, this mechanism produces coordinated emergent behavior, a characteristic of complex adaptive systems (Holland, 1996).

3.2 Coevolution

Coevolution is the process by which different parts of the system simultaneously adapt to external disturbances. In the case of Colombian LPG, there is coevolution between market dynamics, technological advances, and state policy.

For example, new operating conditions resulting from growing demand for cylinders and the digitization of inventory control require changes in regulations.

Each alteration in the environment causes comparable changes in the other components, giving rise to a systematic coevolution process that preserves the sustainability of the industry.

3.3 Stability and adaptive feedback

The adaptive feedback loops in the Colombian LPG system aim to keep it stable in the face of external disturbances such as the devaluation of the peso or changes in world oil prices.

Despite the cyclical fluctuations characteristic of nonlinear dynamic systems, these feedback mechanisms allow the system to maintain its functional integrity.

4. Conversation

The analysis allows us to confirm that the Colombian liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) market should be considered a complex adaptive socio-technical system, with many interdependent actors and feedback links that determine its stability or instability.

Organizational cybernetics and complexity theories (Ríos, 200i) provide a solid basis for understanding how the sector reacts to changes in its technological, legal, and economic environment.

The results show that the industry exhibits emerging dynamics and nonlinear trends when viewed from a complexity perspective Contreras (2007). This can be seen in how prices react to slight changes in supply or regulation, in how adaptive commercial practices, as well as in the presence of delays that affect the equilibrium of the system.

Traditional mechanistic models fall short in this regard (Contreras, 2012), as they do not take into account the feedback effects of public and private actions, nor the interdependence of variables.

According to organizational cybernetics, the Ministry of Mines and Energy, the CREG, the UPME, the SSPD, and private companies make up the institutional framework of the Colombian energy industry, which functions as a functional distributed system.

The basis of organizational viability is feedback and communication between different levels, Espinosa (2011).

The study also highlights the crucial importance of collective intelligence for the LPG sector. The system's adaptability is reinforced by the exchange of information between public and private entities. Initiatives for data interoperability, energy monitoring, and information-sharing platforms can become complex governance systems, Teisman (2014).

In practice, this conceptual framework allows us to suggest energy resilience tactics that emphasize diversification of supply sources and prediction of disruptions. If the system is able to preserve its organizational and regulatory flexibility, LPG can serve as a bridge between fossil fuels and clean energy in a context of global energy transition.

5. Conclusions

The LPG system in Colombia is complex and flexible. Numerous nonlinear interactions between prices, demand, regulation, and technology affect its dynamics and structure. Self-organization, coevolution, and adaptive feedback are three new patterns that show that an organization is dynamic and constantly changing.

Energy governance is reinforced by collective intelligence. Collaboration between organizations and companies makes it possible to provide common information and well-founded options, which improves the flexibility and efficiency of the system.

Emerging self-organizing behaviors can be observed in the LPG business. Without the need for centralized control, decentralized decisions made by stakeholders (consumers, companies, and regulators) consistently lead to global outcomes, demonstrating that complexity can bring order rather than chaos.

The secret to energy planning is a dynamic and holistic approach. It would be feasible to predict supply, demand, and price scenarios using simulation models (such as Vensim or Stella), which would increase the decision-making capacity of both the private and government sectors.

6. Recommendations on energy policy and LPG competitiveness

In light of the results and the complex systems approach, the following suggestions are offered to Colombian energy policymakers and organizations involved in the LPG industry:

To increase information synchronization and responsiveness to disruptions, strengthen institutional feedback by establishing a National LPG Observatory that combines data from the UPME, CREG, SSPD, and companies in the sector.

Implement real-information systems on prices, demand, and storage using big data and machine learning technology.

Use dynamic models for the development of energy plans.

Evaluate demand elasticity, energy transition scenarios, and subsidy strategies using systemic simulation tools (Vensim, Stella).

To improve understanding of feedback effects and delays, the technical teams of state entities should receive training in systemic thinking and system dynamics.

Promote flexibility in regulations

Create adaptable regulatory frameworks that avoid reactive judgments, allowing for automatic adjustments in response to changes in international prices or exchange rates.

Promote corporate self-regulation programs based on technological innovation and risk management.

To produce creative energy solutions, foster collective sectoral intelligence and establish channels for inter-institutional co-creation between government, industry, and academia.

Integrate collaborative platforms and knowledge networks that facilitate mutual learning and the exchange of best practices.

Promote the technological fusion of clean energy sources (hydrogen, solar thermal energy, and biogas) with LPG.

Encourage renewable LPG (BioLPG) pilot projects, backed by financial and fiscal incentives. Promote energy equity and sustainability plans, giving priority to rural areas with low natural gas penetration.

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